

ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY AND PERFORMANCE OF FOOD AND BEVERAGES MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN ENUGU STATE.

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Abstract: The study evaluated Environmental sustainability and performance of food and beverages manufacturing Firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to: examine the relationship between operational risk management and output; and the relationship between use of resources and profitability of food and beverages in Enugu state. The descriptive survey design was used. A total population of 988 selected staff of the study organizations. The adequate sample size of two hundred and seventy-seven (277) using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. Two hundred and two hundred and Forty-Six (246) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data were presented and analyzed using mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using the Pearson correlation (r). The findings indicated that There was significant positive relationship between Operational risk management and the output $r(95, n= 246) = .451 <.769, p <.05$) and there was significant positive relationship between use of resources and profitability of food and beverages as reported in the probability value of $r(95, n= 246), = .481 <.719, p <.05$). The study concluded that Operational risk management and use of resources had significant positive significant relationship with the output and profitability of food and beverages. The study recommended among others that for effective business continuity and lower compliance costs, management of food and beverages manufacturing firms should put Operational risk management into practice to maintain business resilience and improve efficiency.

Keywords: Environmental, Sustainability, Performance, Food, Beverages, Manufacturing, Firms.

Introduction

1.1 Background of the study

As civilizations realize how urgently they must reduce the effects of human activity on the environment, environmental sustainability has grown in importance on a worldwide scale (United Nations, 2015). As a vital component of the global economy, the food and beverage industry have a major share of the blame for accomplishing sustainable development objectives. This industry is vital to Enugu State, Nigeria, as it drives economic growth and supplies the people with necessities. However, there are issues with environmental sustainability related to the industry's present practices and performance metrics. To protect the welfare of the current and future generations, the idea of environmental sustainability includes minimizing greenhouse gas

emissions, reducing pollution, and using natural resources responsibly (Ugwu, Ebeke, and Igah, 2021). A thorough awareness of the industry's environmental effect, current sustainability strategies, and player performance are necessary to achieve environmental sustainability in the food and beverage sector. Because environmental sustainability is so important to everything else, it is a topic that should receive a lot of attention. Energy-efficient and environmentally friendly technologies that employ renewable energy sources like wind, solar, geothermal, biomass, hydro, or biomass energy, construct compactly, and lower emissions from the production and transportation of power. Because they trap heat in the atmosphere, greenhouse gases (GHG) are the main cause of global warming. Carbon monoxide (CO), which is produced by burning fossil fuels, accounted for 56% of all human greenhouse gases released in 2004. Deforestation-related CO₂ emissions made up the remaining 17% (Shahsavari and Akbari, 2018). Rich natural resources abound in Enugu State, including waterways and arable land (National Bureau of Statistics, 2019). These resources are vital to the food and beverage industry, which boosts the economy. Nevertheless, pollution, careless waste disposal, and unrestrained resource use have led to environmental deterioration and ecological stress in the area.

Moreover, performance is viewed as an area of competence and efficacy that encompasses the financial and operational results inside the company. Training and development programs must not only be competitive but also help the firm on its established strategic path as businesses expand and the talent war heats up (Gorman, 2015). Performance metrics evaluate the stakeholders' level of satisfaction with the company. The food and beverage industry's competitiveness and long-term viability are impacted by its poor sustainability performance. Businesses are under pressure to implement sustainable practices as consumers and regulatory agencies want more ecologically conscious operations and goods. If these requirements are not met, there may be harm to one's reputation, a loss of market share, and restricted access to foreign markets. To address these challenges, it is crucial to assess the environmental sustainability and performance of the food and beverages sector in Enugu State.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The food and beverage industry in Enugu State is facing a serious issue that has to be addressed right away: inadequate environmental sustainability and poor practices. This problem jeopardizes the region's efforts to attain sustainable development goals and presents serious environmental concerns. At the moment, Enugu State's food and beverage industry's operations and performance metrics do not follow sustainable standards.

As a result, the industry's unrestrained resource use adds to the loss of priceless natural resources like energy and water. Inadequate waste management techniques worsen the already serious environmental issues by causing pollutants to rise, dangerous chemicals to be disposed of improperly, and non-biodegradable trash to build up. The many ecosystems of Enugu State as well as the health and wellbeing of the human population are both adversely affected by this environmental deterioration. Moreover, the absence of strong sustainable practices limits the sector's capacity for resilience and long-term growth.

Failure to adopt environmentally friendly technologies and practices not only puts the industry at a competitive disadvantage but also undermines its ability to meet evolving consumer demands for sustainability and responsible production. This can lead to decreased market share, loss of business opportunities, and reputational damage for food and beverage companies operating in Enugu State.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The main objectives of the study were to evaluate the Environmental sustainability and performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the relationship between operational risk management and output of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu state.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between use of resources and profitability of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. What is the relationship between operational risk management and output of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu state?
- ii. What is the relationship between use of resources and profitability of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu state?

1.5 Statement of the Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study

- i. Operational risk management has relationship with the output of food and beverages in Enugu state.
- ii. Use of resources has relationship with profitability of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

1.6 Significance of the study

Expectantly, the findings of the study will be of great interest and benefit to the following organization:

Government: It would assist the government to see the need to promote manufacturing firms especially in the area of environmental changes that will enhance and sustains the firms for growth.

Students: It will be of benefit to the students since it will enable them acquire knowledge on the effect of environmental sustainability and also future researchers for further study.

Organizations: Irrespective of how proper their programmes were articulated they had to take cognizance of their environment. It was on this perspective that the significance of this work could not be understated;

The Researcher: The researcher also stands to gain from the work because it will give a direction to the researcher on how to scan the environment before starting any business for better economic development.

2.0 Review of the Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Environment

It is possible to define the term "environment" as "all those elements which, by their very existence or by virtue of their impact, form the framework, setting, and living conditions for mankind" (Larsson and Aissa, 2019). The biotic, abiotic, physical, chemical, and other natural factors that envelop a living organism's habitat and allow for interaction and adaptation are also referred to as the environment. Therefore, creating a supportive legal and policy framework, as well as ensuring that it is implemented and enforced, institutional strengthening that includes coordination and clearly defined roles and responsibilities of key entities (government, non-state actors, including civil society), building the capacity of all actors to enable them to fulfill their roles, and social dialogue that includes stakeholder participation are all part of creating an enabling environment.

2.1.2 Sustainability

Sustainability in business and policy contexts aims to keep natural or physical resources from running out so they may be used for a long time to come (Daniel and Brown, 2021). According to Grant and Kenton (2019), sustainability is centered on addressing current demands without sacrificing the capacity of future generations to address their own needs. The practice of managing a company while considering its economic, social, and environmental dimensions is known as business sustainability. The triple bottom line strategy is another name for it (Mahajan and Montu, 2018).

2.1.3 Environmental Sustainability

Environmental sustainability may be defined as the act of sustainably engaging with the world. We take this action to prevent the depletion of natural resources and to ensure that the needs of future generations are met. Sustainability in the environment is concerned with the condition of the earth. It inspires people to lead waste-free lives and even renew some of the resources we consume on a daily basis. Humanity must first make significant progress toward environmental sustainability and refrain from acts that damage or deplete the environment in order to preserve its inherent beauty and functions. The application of environmental sustainability and its several subcategories, such as sustainable forestry, energy, and agriculture, will be covered in this lesson (Gillaspy, 2021).

2.1.3.1 Operational risk management

Operational risk is the possibility that occurrences that interfere with corporate operations, rules, procedures, or systems, may result in losses. Errors made by employees, illegal actions like fraud, and natural disasters are a few things that might lead to operational risk. The majority of firms acknowledge that faults will inevitably occur in their people and processes, which will lead to inefficient operations. To minimize risks and guarantee effective responses, operational risk evaluations should place a strong emphasis on doable corrective actions (Morgan, 2022). Operational risk management itself may be enhanced by utilizing new data and implementing new technology. More focused risk management that is carried out more effectively and is fully linked with corporate decision making is achievable (Eceiza, 2020).

2.1.3.2 Use of resources

The abundance of natural resources in Nigeria is the only factor supporting our high quality of living. We utilize water, soil, air, biodiversity, and land as ecosystems and for leisure activities in addition to abiotic and biotic raw resources. We also employ wind, solar, and tidal fluxes for energy. In addition, these resources operate as waste disposal sites, carbon sinks, and essential production inputs for forestry and agriculture (Reinhard, 2019). Natural resources are necessary for the well-being of humans. The clean air we breathe, the vegetables we eat, and the water we drink are essential to our survival. Natural resources are necessary for us to heat our houses and have roofs over our heads. For us to live and prosper, they are essential. The concept of natural resources refers to naturally occurring living and non-living elements of the Earth system, including plants, fish, and fungi, but also water, soil, and minerals.

2.1.4 Performance

When all efforts are directed toward fulfilling customer satisfaction and reaching the predetermined goals, performance is attained. Nonetheless, it is impossible to quantify goals or consumer satisfaction precisely. Performance encompasses both actions and outcomes. The performer's actions are what translate an abstract thought into a tangible action during a performance. Behaviors are results in and of themselves, not only means to an end; they are the consequence of the mental and physical labor that goes into completing activities, and they are assessable independently of outcomes (Bourguignon, 2017). A performance occurs when a play, concert, or other type of entertainment is staged or presented. According to Ivan and Cary (2015), job performance in the workplace refers to the assumed definition or specifications of a function.

2.1.4.1 Output

The term "output" refers to a nation's gross domestic product, which is the total amount of goods and services produced over a specific time period. The phrase can be used to describe all labor, energy, products, or services generated by a machine, factory, or individual (Market Business News, 2022). The number of products or services produced by a company, industry, or nation in a specific amount of time, whether they are consumed or utilized for more production, is known as its output. According to Wikipedia (2013), output is the end product of an economic process that employed inputs to create a good or service that might be purchased or used elsewhere. The metric used to compare production to efficiency is output. It frequently comes up in casual conversation (Down, 2019).

2.1.4.2 Profitability

The capacity of a business to use its assets to produce income beyond its costs is known as profitability. Stated otherwise, this refers to the ability of a business to make money off of its activities. Profit and profitability are closely related, but there is one important difference. While profitability is an absolute idea, profit is a relative one. It is the metric used to evaluate how profitable a business is in relation to its market share. Profitability, which decides whether an undertaking succeeds or fails, is a measure of efficiency (Melissa, 2021).

2.1.5 Conceptual Framework of the study

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Open-system Theory

When biologist Ludwig von Bertalanffy first proposed open system theory in 1956, it was instantly relevant to all fields of study. "All systems are characterized by an assemblage or combination of parts whose relations make them interdependent," is how the idea of a system is defined. The phrase "open systems" represented the emerging notion that every organization is different, partly due to the environment in which it operates, and that it should be designed to handle different possibilities and challenges. For instance, studies conducted in the 1960s showed that in situations when markets or technology were changing quickly, conventional bureaucratic organizations typically did not thrive. Additionally, many were unaware of how crucial local cultural factors are to employee motivation.

2.3 Empirical Review

Ubesie, Chitor, and Ejembi, (2016), conducted a study on effect of Cash Flow Statement on Performance of Selected Food Beverage Companies in Nigeria. The study looks at how cash flow and performance relate to each other in Nigeria's food and beverage industry. Six (6) food and beverage firms that are listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange were surveyed as part of the study. Information was taken from the finances and annual reports of the chosen research businesses. The multiple regression approach was employed to do statistical analysis on the pertinent data. The study's findings showed that corporate success in Nigeria's food and beverage industry is significantly positively correlated with operational and financing cash flows.

Onyekwelu, and Nnadi, (2018), conducted a study on Evaluation of Firms' Corporate Financial Indicators and Operational Performance of Selected Firms in Nigeria. The study looked at how certain Nigerian enterprises' operational performance was affected by their growth indicators. Return on Assets served as the gauge for financial success, while business size and profitability served as surrogates for operational performance. The ex-post facto research design was used in the study. The financial statements of the companies under study provided the data. For the analysis, multiple regressions were employed. The findings indicate that Return on Assets is significantly impacted negatively and marginally by business size and profitability. The report suggests that companies aim to grow their size and profitability at a rate that will have a favorable and notable impact on return on assets.

Ugwu, Adonai, and Orga, (2022), conducted a study on Operational Risk Management Practices and Performance of Aluminum Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State. The performance and operational risk management procedures of aluminum manufacturing companies in the state of Enugu were assessed in the study. The specific goals were to investigate the following relationships: risk avoidance strategy and profitability; response planning and waste reduction; and risk transfer to a third party and customer retention in Enugu State's aluminum manufacturing companies. Simple random sampling and the survey technique were employed in the study. The questionnaire's administration served as the main source of data. The research population comprises the proprietors and employees of the chosen business owners in Enugu city, with a total population of 2, 407, and 47. Using the Cochran (1963) sampling approach, the sample size of 331 was calculated with a 5 percent margin of error. A total of 287 employees responded the completed questionnaire

with accuracy. Using the Sprint Likert Scale, the data were presented and evaluated by mean score and standard deviation. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was used to examine the hypotheses. The results showed a substantial positive correlation between profitability and risk avoidance ($r=.548 <.870$, $p<.05$). Waste reduction and response planning revealed a strong positive association ($r=.672 <.838$ $p<.05$).

Ndubuisi-Okolo, and Anekwe, Nwanonigwe, and Onuzulike, (2022), conducted a study on Effect of Strategic Orientation on Performance of Food and Beverage Firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. This work focused attention on effect of strategic orientation on Food and Beverage Firms in Enugu State. Specifically, it delved into the effect of market orientation on the market share of Food and Beverage Firms in Enugu State. The study used a structured questionnaire that was set up to capture the study's unique purpose, hence a survey research methodology was used. Two hundred (200) people in all were taken out of the registered food and beverage companies in Enugu State. Using a census sampling method allowed for the inclusion of all participants. A five-point Likert scale was used in the structured questionnaire design to elicit responses from the respondents and collect data. Simple Regression Analysis was used to test the hypothesis once the data were created and descriptively assessed. The outcome showed that, in Enugu State, market orientation significantly increased the market share of food and beverage companies.

Bello, (2022), conducted a study on Effect of Risk Management on the Financial Performance of Food and Beverage Industries in Nigeria. This paper aims to examine the effect of risk management on the performance of food and beverages company in Nigeria, in apply this, proxies were introduced (operational and liquidity risk) to examine their effect on the financial performance of food and beverages company in Nigeria. Using co-integrated regression analysis techniques and the Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test (ADF) method of data analysis, the study uses an ex-post facto and time series research design. The analysis examines ten listed food and beverage companies that were quoted between 2010 and 2021 on the Nigeria Stock Exchange. The study's conclusions indicate that operational and liquidity risks have a negative relationship, albeit a negligible one, with return on asset. Regression analysis further demonstrates that, for the study periods, operational and liquidity risks had no discernible impact on return on asset (ROA).

Kalu, (2016), established a study on Corporate Governance and Profitability of Listed Food and Beverages Firms in Nigeria. A company's primary objective is to achieve long-term profitability. Moreover, corporate governance needs to endeavor to guarantee this consistent upswing in organizational performance. Various scientific domains have given understanding the effect of corporate governance on business profitability more attention throughout time. The purpose of this study was to investigate the connection between corporate governance and business profitability using data from eight food and beverage companies that were listed between 2004 and 2014 on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. In a panel data context, the data were analyzed using multiple regression utilizing Ordinary Least Squares along with basic descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings showed a positive correlation between board size and net assets per share and return on equity at the

five percent significance level. On the other hand, there is a positive correlation between board composition and net assets per share, but a negative correlation with return on equity.

Orshi, and Yunusa, (2016), conducted a study on Liquidity Management and Profitability of Listed Food and Beverages Companies in Nigeria. This study examines the relationship between liquidity management and profitability of listed food and beverages companies in Nigeria over a 10-year period from 2004 to 2013. Ten companies were selected as a sample size from among Nigeria's 21 listed food and beverage companies. An ex-post facto research design was used in the study. The yearly reports and accounts of the selected companies provided the panel data, which was then analyzed using multiple regression analysis and descriptive statistics. According to the analysis, the cash conversion cycle has a negligible detrimental effect on earnings per share and return on equity, respectively. The study suggests that by reducing the firms' cash conversion cycle to a reasonable minimum, management of listed food and beverage companies in Nigeria may optimize the return to shareholders.

Hussaini, Garba, and Idris, (2016), conducted a study on corporate liquidity and profitability of listed food and beverages firms in Nigeria. Throughout the regular course of business, the company's financial stability is largely dependent on the management of corporate liquidity. Examining the relationship between corporate liquidity and profitability of Nigerian listed food and beverage companies is the aim of this research. The six-year research period runs from 2009 to 2014. From the annual reports and accounts of the companies, data for the study was taken. Following the OLS regression, the data was empirically checked between the dependent and independent variables, and a robustness test was performed to ensure the validity of statistical judgments. Robust OLS was used in the multiple regression analysis to test the study's model. The analysis's findings showed that, while accounts receivable was found to be inversely significantly related to ROA of Listed Food and Beverage Firms in Nigeria, quick ratio, accounts payable, IFRS, firm size, and ROA of Listed Food and Beverage Firms in Nigeria showed a strong positive relationship. Although not statistically significant, the cash conversion cycle had an unfavorable relationship with ROA.

Sun, and Chen. (2022), conducted a study on Empirical Study on Relationship between Firm's Working Capital Management and Profitability. The goal of the article is to determine the link between profitability and working capital management, with an emphasis on how industry differences affect this relationship. We discovered a negative correlation between the cash conversion cycle (CCC) and profitability of companies in the consumer goods and services sector, as well as a statistically significant association between the CCC and its components and profitability as evaluated by Tobin Q. These findings suggest that companies should make sure their working capital is managed appropriately, paying particular attention to the cash conversion cycle and its component. This is because effective working capital management is anticipated to increase a company's market value.

3.0 Methodology

The area of the study comprised of five (5) selected food and beverages manufacturing Firms in Enugu metropolis. These firms include: Agro Prospero Nigeria Limited, 194, Abakaliki Road, Emene, Alstate Agric And Property Consultants Ltd, 2, Amokwe Street, Uwani, Aqua Ralph Investment, 9th mile, Ben Merko

Limited, 21, C to C Plaza, Npkonkiti and Juhel company, Nkwobur, Ememe. The choice of these firms was due to high number of staffs, Capital base above 10 million naira. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 988 selected staff of the study organizations. The adequate sample size of two hundred and seventy-seven (277) using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. Two hundred and two hundred and Forty-Six (246) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 86 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.860 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) statistic tool.

4.0 Data presentation and Analyses

4.1 The relationship between operational risk management and output of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

Table 4.1.1: Responses on the relationship between operational risk management and output of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Operational risk assure business continuity and productivity	480	248	144	58	41	971	3.59	1.506	Agree
		96	64	16	29	41	246			
		39.0	26.0	6.5	11.8	16.7	100%			
2	The lowering of complained costs increased the quantity of products	365	256	75	36	66	798	3.24	1.595	Agree
		73	64	25	18	66	246			
		29.7	26.0	10.2	7.3	26.8	100%			
3	The control activities associated with operational risk management streamline decision –making,	410	312	78	40	40	880	3.58	1.434	Agree
		82	78	26	20	40	246			
		33.3	31.7	10.6	8.1	16.3	100%			
4	The operational risk aids in calculating the uncertainties predating their impacts.	480	280	21	84	31	896	3.64	1.455	Agree
		96	70	7	42	31	246			
		39.0	28.5	2.8	17.1	12.6	100%			
5	Risk assessments reduce the chance of incidents occurring and demonstrate to employees and external bodies.	450	280	54	40	48	872	3.54	1.524	Agree
		90	70	18	20	48	246			
		36.6	28.5	7.3	8.1	19.5	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.518	1.5028	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.1.1, 160 respondents out of 246 representing 65.0 percent agreed that operational risk assure business continuity and productivity with mean score 3.59 and standard deviation of 1.506. The lowering of complained costs increased the quantity of products 137 respondents representing 55.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.24 and standard deviation of 1.595. The control activities associated with operational risk management streamline decision –making 160 respondents representing 65.0 percent agreed with mean score of 3.58 and standard deviation of 1.434. The operational risk aids in calculating the uncertainties and predating their impacts 166 respondents representing 67.5 percent agreed with mean score of 3.64 and 1.455. Risk assessments reduce the chance of incidents occurring and also demonstrate to employees and external bodies 160 respondents representing 65.1 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.54 and standard deviation 1.524.

4.2 The relationship between use of resources and profitability of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Table 4.2.1: Responses on the relationship between use of resources and profitability of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

	5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	∑FX	- X	SD	Decision
1 Manager’s real time visibility into employees improved efficiency.	455 91 37.0	356 89 36.2	21 7 2.8	88 44 17.9	15 15 6.1	935 246 100%	3.80	1.277	Agree
2 The managers having greater control over delivery generates incomes to the organisation.	360 72 29.3	356 89 36.2	3 1 .4	76 38 15.4	46 46 18.7	841 246 100%	3.42	1.506	Agree
3 Creating equitable and sustained access to natural resources reduces costs.	400 80 32.5	364 91 37.0	18 6 2.4	80 40 16.3	29 29 11.8	891 246 100%	3.62	1.388	Agree
4 Ensuring that right resources are available at the right time promotes income generation.	405 81 32.9	296 74 30.1	69 23 9.3	12 6 2.4	62 62 25.2	844 246 100%	3.43	1.573	Agree
5 Cost for successful project completion sustains the business.	510 102 41.5	236 59 24.0	42 14 5.7	86 43 17.5	28 28 11.4	902 246 100%	3.67	1.447	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.588	1.4382	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.2.1, 180 respondents out of 246 representing 73.2 percent agreed that Manager’s real time visibility into employees improved efficiency with mean score 3.80 and standard deviation of 1.277. The managers having greater control over delivery generates incomes to the organization 161 respondents representing 65.5 percent

agreed with mean score of 3.42 and standard deviation of 1.506. Creating equitable and sustained access to natural resources reduces costs 171 respondents representing 69.5 percent agreed with mean score of 3.62 and standard deviation of 1.388. Ensuring that right resources are available at the right time promotes income generation 155 respondents representing 63.0 percent agreed with mean score of 3.43 and 1.573. Cost for successful project completion sustains the business 161 respondents representing 65.5 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.67 and standard deviation 1.447.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

4.3.1 Hypothesis One: Operational risk management has relationship with the output of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

Correlations

	Operational risk assure business continuity and productivity	The lowering of complained costs increased the quantity of products	The control activities associated with operational risk management streamline decision-making,	The operational risk aids in calculating the uncertainties and predating their impacts.	Risk assessments reduce the chance of incidents occurring and also demonstrate to employees and external bodies.
Operational risk assure business continuity and productivity Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1	.674** .000	.662** .000	.575** .000	.592** .000
The lowering of complained costs increased the quantity of products Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.674** .000	1	.577** .000	.456** .000	.451** .000
The control activities associated with operational risk management streamline decision-making, Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.662** .000	.577** .000	1	.577** .000	.769** .000
The operational risk aids in calculating the uncertainties and predating their impacts. Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.575** .000	.456** .000	.577** .000	1	.648** .000
Risk assessments reduce the chance of incidents occurring and also demonstrate to employees and external bodies. Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.592** .000	.451** .000	.769** .000	.648** .000	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.3.1. Showed the Pearson correlation matrix on Operational risk management and the output showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .451 <.769. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there was

positive significant relationship between Operational risk management and the output of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu state. ($r = .451 < .769$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .451 < .769, p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .451 < .769$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there was positive significant relationship between Operational risk management and the output of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu state as reported in the probability value of ($r = .451 < .769, p < .05$).

4.3.2 Hypothesis Two: Use of resources has relationship with profitability of food and beverages manufacturing firms.

Correlations

	Manager’s real time visibility into employees improved efficiency.	The managers having greater control over delivery generates incomes to the organisation.	Creating equitable and sustained access to natural resources reduces costs.	Ensuring that right resources are available at the right time promotes income generation.	Cost for successful project completion sustains the business.
Manager’s real time visibility into employees improved efficiency. Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1	.719** .000	.718** .000	.579** .000	.585** .000
The managers having greater control over delivery generates incomes to the organisation. Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.719** .000	1	.732** .000	.582** .000	.587** .000
Creating equitable and sustained access to natural resources reduces costs. Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.718** .000	.732** .000	1	.583** .000	.565** .000
Ensuring that right resources are available at the right time promotes income generation. Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.579** .000	.582** .000	.583** .000	1	.481** .000
Cost for successful project completion sustains the business. Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.585** .000	.587** .000	.565** .000	.481** .000	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.4.2. Showed the Pearson correlation matrix on use of resources and profitability showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.481 < .719$. This value indicates that correlation was significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there was positive significant relationship between use of resources and profitability of food and beverages manufacturing firms in

Enugu State ($r = .481 < .719$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .481 < .719, p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .481 < .719$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there was positive significant relationship between use of resources and profitability of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu State as reported in the probability value of ($r = .481 < .719, p < .05$).

5.0 Summary of the findings

- i. There was significant positive relationship between Operational risk management and the output of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu state as reported in the probability value of $r(95, n = 246) = .451 < .769, p < .05$.
- ii. There was significant positive relationship between use of resources and profitability of food and beverages manufacturing firms in Enugu State as reported in the probability value of $r(95, n = 246), = .481 < .719, p < .05$.

5.1 Conclusion

The study concluded that Operational risk management and use of resources had significant positive significant relationship with the output and profitability of food and beverages. However, the industry's current practices and performance indicators raise concerns regarding environmental sustainability. The concept of environmental sustainability encompasses the responsible use of natural resources, reduction of pollution, and mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions to ensure the well-being of present and future generations. Achieving environmental sustainability in the food and beverages sector requires a comprehensive understanding of the sector's environmental impact, existing sustainability practices, and the performance of industry players.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. For effective business continuity and lower compliance costs, management of food and beverages manufacturing firms should put Operational risk management into practice to maintain business resilience and improve efficiency.
2. A judicious balance should be maintained between exploitation of resources and its replenishment for provision of income, and raw material to satisfy the needs and comforts of human beings.

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